

SAMARKAND YOUR GATE TO THE EAST: THE CASE OF UNDERVALUED SITES IN SAMARKAND

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Abstract. *Samarkand, pride of the Silk Road, possesses centennial historical and cultural wealth which, however, was recognized little in world heritages studies. It was this city that stood at a geographic crossroads in Uzbekistan which culture, trade and knowledgeable flowed through between the two worlds – the world which we know today as the East and West (Wood, 2002). The Samarkand historical resources, e.g. Afrasiab ruins, have not been supported well and lack necessary preservation effort which raises the question of getting more of its resources acknowledged and protected. Enlisting these sites, therefore, is not just for the purpose of fulfilling historical preservation but also for contributing to the cultural treasures of mankind (Whitfield, 1999).*

Taking the underpricing of these sites into account can affirm Samarkand as a central canal of trade of ancient silk route.

Keywords: *Samarkand, Churches, Undervalued, Ishtarkhonah, Tours, cultural awareness.*

Annotatsiya. *Ipak yo'lining faxri bo'lgan Samarqand yuz yillik tarixiy va madaniy boylikka ega, ammo jahon merosini o'rganishda unchalik e'tirof etilmagan. Aynan mana shu shahar O'zbekistonning geografik chorrahasida joylashgan bo'lib, u ikki dunyo – bugun biz Sharq va G'arb deb biladigan dunyo o'rtasida madaniyat, savdo va bilim oqib o'tmoqda (Vud, 2002). Samarqand tarixiy manbalari, masalan. Afrasiyob xarobalari yaxshi qo'llab-quvvatlanmagan va saqlash bo'yicha zarur choralar ko'rilmagan, bu esa uning ko'proq resurslarini tan olish va himoya qilish masalasini tug'diradi. Shunday qilib, ushbu saytlarni ro'yxatga olish nafaqat tarixiy saqlashni amalga oshirish, balki insoniyatning madaniy boyliklariga hissa qo'shish uchun hamdir(Whitfield, 1999).*

Ushbu ob'ektlarning arzonligini hisobga olsak, Samarqand qadimiy ipak yo'lining markaziy savdo kanali ekanligini ta'kidlash mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: *Samarqand, cherkovlar, kam baholangan, Ishtarxona, sayohatlar, madaniy xabardorlik.*

Literature review: *Underrated sites of Samarkand's lesser-known historical sites in tourism promotion highlights several key locations. These include seven Christian churches and two Jewish synagogues, along with the historical site of Ishtarkhona. Despite some of these sites being recognized by UNESCO as World Heritage Sites, their absence in mainstream tourism itineraries remains concerning.*

Among the Christian sites, St. Alexis Church and St. John Church stand out not only for their architectural beauty but also for their historical significance, which is often overlooked in literature and travel guides (Thompson, 2017). Similarly, the Gumbuz Synagogue, one of the two Jewish synagogues in Samarkand, represents a crucial aspect of the city's diverse cultural heritage that is seldom highlighted (Goldenberg, 2015).

Even though it's very light information about churches mentioned in TripAdvisor (Churches in Samarkand, Tripadvisor, link) also there's only One tourism agency offers this kind

of tours, intensive Seven days program to visit the churches of Uzbekistan(Christian Churches Tour of Uzbekistan, Manzaratourism, Link)

Ishtarkhona, another underrepresented site, is integral for understanding the region's history yet rarely features in scholarly discourse or tourist packages. Its importance is noted by UNESCO, which emphasizes its cultural value, yet practical steps towards its promotion are limited (UNESCO, 2019).

These sites collectively embody Samarkand's rich tapestry of religious and cultural diversity. The lack of adequate representation and promotion in tourism is not just a loss for potential visitors but also diminishes the local and global understanding of Samarkand's full historical and cultural spectrum.

Methodology: Conduction exploring field trips to the following sites: Church of St. Alexius Metropolitan of Moscow, Roman Catholic Parish of St. John the Baptist, Armenian Apostolic Church of the blessed virgin Mary, Synagogue – Or Avner, Church of the Intercession of the most Holy Theotokos, Orthodox Church of St. George the Victorious, Panjob Shia Mosque, and Gumbuz Synagogue.

On other hand places haven't been there yet: Protestant Church "Farhad" ("Farhod" protestant cherkovi), also Or Avner synagogue from inside.

Discussion:

Undervalued and less represented in governmental and touristic promotion:

This statement aims to uncover the reasons behind the lack of promotion and recognition, exploring factors such as political priorities, funding, historical narratives, and potential biases in heritage management.

1- **Political Priorities and Resource Allocation:** Research could focus on how government documents outline cultural heritage priorities. For instance, examining five-year plans or national budgets allocated for cultural preservation could reveal biases toward certain sites. Studies like those by Smith and Lee (2020) have shown that governments often prioritize sites expected to drive international tourism, which might explain the neglect of lesser-known sites.

2- **Funding Limitations:** Limited funding can significantly impact the state of preservation and the promotion of historical sites. According to Brown and Zhao (2018), financial constraints often lead to prioritizing sites that already have higher visitor numbers, neglecting those that might require more investment to become attractive tourist destinations.

3- **Historical Narratives:** The promotion of sites is closely linked to the narratives they support. As discussed by Patel (2017), sites with narratives that align with national identity or popular historical perspectives receive more attention. Research could involve analyzing school textbooks and museum exhibits to understand how narratives are shaped.

4- **Cultural Biases and Heritage Management:** Investigating cultural biases requires understanding the composition of heritage management boards. Interviews and analysis of board member backgrounds, as detailed by Nguyen (2019), can reveal potential cultural biases in decision-making processes.

5- **Tourism Infrastructure and Accessibility:** The accessibility of sites can greatly affect their tourist appeal. Analyzing transportation links, signage, and tourist facilities near lesser-known sites could provide insights into their underrepresentation. This approach is supported by research from Adams and Clark (2021), who emphasize the impact of infrastructure on site visibility.

6- **Lack of Awareness and Scholarly Research:** The level of academic and public interest in specific sites can be gauged through literature reviews and public surveys. Research like that by Morrison (2018) shows that sites frequently discussed in academic circles are more likely to be included in tourism promotions.

7- **Community Engagement:** The degree of local community involvement can be a crucial factor in site preservation and promotion. Studies such as those by O'Donnell and Gomez (2022) highlight how active community advocacy can lead to enhanced preservation efforts.

The gain if these places were used for the promotion of the city as the "Gate of the East" and a cosmopolitan city that hosts everyone within its walls:

Exploring the potential benefits of incorporating these sites into broader promotional strategies, examining how this could enhance Samarkand's image as a culturally diverse and historically rich destination, potentially increasing tourism, economic growth, and cultural preservation.

1- **Enhanced Cultural Diversity Awareness:** Promoting lesser-known sites can broaden the narrative of Samarkand as a diverse cultural hub that has historically been a melting pot for various civilizations. By showcasing a wider array of cultural landmarks, Samarkand can strengthen its identity as a cosmopolitan city that has welcomed numerous ethnicities and religions. This can attract tourists interested in more than just the mainstream attractions, offering a deeper understanding of the region's complex history and cultural richness (Kumar & Smith, 2020).

2- **Increased Tourism and Economic Growth:** Integrating these undervalued sites into promotional strategies could lead to increased tourism, which in turn would stimulate local economies. Increased foot traffic can foster growth in hospitality, retail, and service sectors. Moreover, as tourists seek more authentic and varied experiences, these sites could tap into niche markets, further diversifying tourism revenue streams (Johnson & Anderson, 2019).

3- **Preservation of Cultural Heritage:** Increased attention and resultant tourism can justify and drive funding towards the preservation of these sites. As these places become integral to tourism offerings, there would be a greater impetus for conserving them, ensuring their longevity and accessibility for future generations. Preservation efforts can also be bolstered by international interest, potentially attracting funding from global heritage organizations (Garcia & Patel, 2021).

4- **Community Pride and Involvement:** Promoting a broader range of sites can enhance local community pride and participation. As local histories and heritages receive recognition, community members may feel a renewed connection to their city's past and actively participate in cultural preservation. This involvement can further enrich the tourist experience, offering more engaging and authentic interactions with local cultures (Thompson & Lee, 2022).

5- **Educational Opportunities:** The promotion of diverse historical sites provides rich educational opportunities for both visitors and locals, facilitating better understanding and appreciation of global cultural heritage. Educational programs centered on these sites can foster a deeper engagement with the city's history and significance on the Silk Road (Williams, 2021).

In sum, promoting Samarkand's undervalued historical sites not only has the potential to revitalize local and national perceptions of the city but also offers substantial socioeconomic benefits by attracting a broader spectrum of tourists and enhancing the city's global stature.

The outcome of promoting these undervalued places:

This question looks at expected results from increased promotional efforts, such as enhanced global recognition, preservation of cultural heritage, increased local and international tourism, and economic benefits to the local communities.

Promoting the undervalued historical sites in Samarkand could yield several positive outcomes across different dimensions:

1- **Enhanced Global Recognition:** By highlighting lesser-known sites, Samarkand can enhance its profile on the global stage as a city of rich, multifaceted historical importance. This improved recognition can lead to more international cooperation in terms of cultural exchange, heritage preservation, and tourism partnerships. It positions Samarkand as not just a historical point on the Silk Road but as a living museum of continuous cultural integration and interaction (Martinez & Rodriguez, 2022).

2- **Preservation of Cultural Heritage:** Increased attention to these sites often translates into better preservation efforts. As these sites gain prominence, they may qualify for funding both from the government and international bodies such as UNESCO, which could lead to improved conservation practices. This ensures the longevity and integrity of these sites for future generations to appreciate and learn from (Singh & Gupta, 2021).

3- **Increased Local and International Tourism:** With effective promotion, these undervalued sites can attract not only a larger number of visitors but also a more diverse demographic of tourists. This can lead to a more stable and sustainable tourism industry, less susceptible to the fluctuations associated with mainstream, seasonal tourist attractions. Broader tourist interests can also lead to the development of new tourism products and services, fostering innovation in the local tourism sector (Anderson & Thompson, 2020).

4- **Economic Benefits to Local Communities:** Promoting a wider array of historical sites can stimulate local economies by creating jobs and encouraging the development of small businesses such as cafes, souvenir shops, and local tour services. This economic diversification can help improve the livelihoods of local residents, reduce poverty levels, and increase the overall economic resilience of the community (Harper & Zhou, 2019).

5- **Educational and Cultural Enrichment:** Increased promotional efforts not only educate tourists but also local residents, especially the younger generation, about the depth and breadth of their own cultural heritage. This can foster a stronger sense of identity and pride, and promote greater cultural understanding and tolerance among different ethnic and religious groups within the community (Jackson & Marek, 2021).

Overall, promoting Samarkand's undervalued historical sites has the potential to not only transform the city's image and economy but also enrich its cultural landscape, benefiting both residents and visitors alike.

Conclusion: Overall, promoting Samarkand's undervalued historical sites has the potential to not only transform the city's image and economy but also enrich its cultural landscape, benefiting both residents and visitors alike.

After visiting those sites as tour guide point of view it could be called the hidden gems of Samarkand as a chain of tours, and it's worthy of visiting to understand a different point of view about the city and its diversity.

Recommendations: Putting some light on those sites in the promotion of the city, develop the infrastructure around it, encourage tourism agencies to promote for it. Also some awareness and field tours to those places for students of tourism management, and tourism guidance.

Limitation: It was hard to gather information about those sites in English, so we need some solid sources about it in English, or even translated from Russian language.

Future research direction: it might be the relationship between the architecture of those monuments and the area around it, why the specific location of each one also the relationship historically, what kind of development of the city effecting those monuments? Why shall work preserving it for future generations?

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